

Do Mergers And Acquisition Result In What They Target For? An Analysis Of Corporate Governance And Mergers And Acquisition In Pakistan

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Abstract

*This study examines the effect of corporate governance (CG) on M&A transactions (deal activity) by measuring financial performance on the Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE) for non-financial companies from 1993 to 2014, focusing on SG and CFOA. Prior studies failed to include this firm's return on asset (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) in their calculations, whereas others have estimated return on asset (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and Tobin's q. In order to reach this goal, the research will provide more evidence on whether CG, which is found in some developing countries, increases M&A financial performance in a developing country like Pakistan. The research shows that, in the absence of CFOA, an increase in SG price will lead to an increase in CFOA value. Financial performance of acquiring firms in Pakistan changes in accordance with interaction variables such as PM*BS and PM*BI. M&A firms will likely prioritize independence on the board and the size of the board to achieve positive financial performance. According to the current literature, an effective CG mechanism is necessary for the value of the firm to be increased, especially during M&A.*

Introduction

Market for corporate control (MCC) plays an important role in companies' performance. MCC is a market of distinct managerial teams who compete for the control rights of a company (Jensen & Ruback, 1983). It is also called external corporate control (Colcera, 2007). MCC plays its role as a last resort when the firm's internal governance (board of directors) underperforms (Fama, 1980). MCC is the market for mergers and acquisitions (M&A) (Larcker, 2011). M&A is used as a tool for better financial performance of the firms and for survival in global competition (Laneve & Stüllein, 2010). A firm, when not capable of performing and attain its costs are either merged or acquired to obtain profit and to acquire a competitive edge over others (Arshad, 2012). Moreover, M&A results in cost efficiency and performance efficiency. However, others report that firms do not gain from M&A (see e.g., Selcuk & Yilmaz, 2011; Kemal, 2011). These studies conclude that merged and acquired firms negative performance is due to lack of effective corporate governance (CG) system in the firms. Due to lack of effective CG, the manager's motivates for self-interest and through M&A managers' accomplish interest of expropriation which results in a decrease in shareholders' value (Nazir, Ali & Haque, 2009). CG aligns managements' interests with shareholders' interests and thus increases firm performance even for M&A firms (Epps & Cereola, 2008; Chaghadari, 2011).

Most of the studies examine the impact of CG on M&A performance in developed countries (Frederiksen & Jessen, 2006; Carline et al., 2009). However, this area is not studied in depth especially in developing countries. In Pakistan the only study is of Afza and Nazir (2012) on the role of CG in operating performance of M&A firms. The earlier studies use different proxies for firms' performance such as ROA, ROE and Tobin's q. This study uses sales growth (SG) and cash flow over assets (CFOA) as measures of firm performance. SG and CFOA are indicators of firm financial performance in the following studies (for e.g., Stahl & Voigt, 2004; Majumdar, Moussawi & Yaylacicegi, 2007). Therefore, its need to empirically examine the impact of CG on financial performance of merged and acquired firms of Pakistan.

Literature Review

In the era of global competition, M&A is used as a means for existence in the competition (Laneve & Stüllein, 2010). Arshad (2012) states that firms that are not able to perform well and cannot bear the costs, thus those firms are merged or acquired in order to achieve high profits and competitive advantage. Some studies report that M&A improves performance such as cost, profit and performance efficiencies (Beccalli & Frantz, 2009;

Nedunchezhia & Premalatha, 2013). However, others report that M&A result in loss for a firm. The reason for the decrease in M&A performance due to lack of effective CG mechanisms (Kleinschmidt, 2007).

Previous studies investigate the relationship between CG and M&A performance and find a positive relationship between CG and M&A performance. However, these studies provide evidence from capital markets in developed countries. According to Frederiksen and Jessen (2006) and De Jong, Van der Poel, and Wolfswinkel (2007), CG mechanisms improve M&A performance. However, in emerging and developing countries, this issue is understudied and yields inconclusive results.

Prior literature shows that ROA, ROE and Tobin's q are the measures of firm's performance. However, others used SG and CFOA to measure financial performance of firm after M&A (Majumdar et al., 2007). They argue that SG and CFOA are also good measures of financial performance of M&A firms. The primary objective of M&A firm's manager is to achieve rise in SG, relative sales volume and synergy benefit from M&A (Baumol, 1959 cited in Majumdar et al., 2007). Therefore, this study uses SG and CFOA as proxies for financial performance after M&A for firms listed at KSE while taking into account the CG mechanisms.

Hypotheses Development and Research Method

M&A as an approach for growth have received much consideration from not only developed economies but also from developing economies (Ferraz & Hamaguchi, 2002; Sanda & Adjei-Benin, 2011). Moreover, the findings of Healy et al. (1992) suggest that merger enhances the firm's performance. Others report contrasting results. As discussed in chapter 2, one of the reasons behind the negative performance of M&A firms is the lack of effective CG system in the firms. Furthermore, Carline et al. (2009) provide evidence that CG improves the performance of the acquiring firms.

Several studies have looked into the relationship between CG and M&A performance. The returns on assets, returns on equity, and Tobin's q were used as measures of firm performance in these studies. A comparison between financial performance measures is made using SG and CFOA (see e.g., Stahl & Voigt, 2004; Majumdar et al., 2007). Furthermore, the primary goal of the companies is to achieve the highest possible SG and relative sales volumes (Baumol, 1959 cited in Majumdar et al., 2007). Prices will rise if the value of CFOA rises in the absence of SG, and market power will be used to achieve this result (Kumar, 1984 cited in Majumdar et al., 2007). It is possible; on the other hand, that it increases in the presence of SG, which indicates that, on the revenue side, the merged firms realized synergies benefits by increasing the volume of sales with the combined assets, which indicates that the merged firms are more profitable. Although the negative value demonstrates the inability of merged firms to achieve synergies, the positive value demonstrates the ability (Farrell & Shapiro, 1990). As a result, the arguments presented above provide a framework for investigating the impact of CG on the performance of Pakistani M&A firms. As a result, the following hypothesis is proposed by the research:

H1: There is no relation between CG mechanisms and post M&A financial performance.

This study uses data from the period 1993-2014 taken from Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE). The sample consists of 21 non-financial companies listed at KSE. The data regarding acquiring firms two years pre and two years after M&A period is collected. The data is collected only for acquiring firms. The data is collected from the annual reports of the selected sample companies.

The study proposes the following multivariate regression model to investigate the effect of CG on M&A performance;

$$\text{Fin_Perf} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{CG} + \beta_2 \text{PM} + \beta_3 \text{Control} + \epsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where Fin_Perf is the financial performance of acquiring firms which is proxied by SG and CFOA; CG is the corporate governance variables which are proxied by board independence (BI), CEO duality (CEOd) and board size (BS); Post M&A variable is proxied by PM, PM is taken as 1 if the M&A takes place, otherwise 0, post M&A also represent the interaction of PM with CG variables (such as PM*BI, PM*CEOd, PM*BS); Control variables are proxied by firm size (FS), industry relatedness (IR), industry (IND) and YEAR; ϵ_i represents the error term.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the dependent and independent variables. The mean and the median of Log SG is 2.75 and 2.71. While the mean of CFOA is 0.89 and the median of CFOA is 0.68. The standard deviations for SG and CFOA are 0.90 and 2.16. Moreover, the mean and median of BS is 7.80 and 7 and the median of both CEOd and BI is 0. Whereas the mean and median for FS is 5.95 and 6.26. Furthermore, the median for both the IR and PM is same 1. The skewness and kurtosis of all the variables indicate that the data are normally distributed.

Table 1 : Descriptive statistics of dependent and independent variables

Variables	Mean	Median	StDev	Min	Max	Skew	Kurt
Log SG	2.75	2.71	0.90	0.25	5.13	0.01	2.82
CFOA	0.89	0.68	2.16	-5.25	9.39	0.81	3.27

BS	7.80	7.00	1.27	7.00	13.0	1.83	3.25
CEOd	0.35	0.00	0.48	0.00	1.00	0.62	-1.65
BI	0.13	0.00	0.34	0.00	1.00	2.15	2.66
FS	5.95	6.26	2.09	2.73	9.98	0.30	-1.10
IR	0.81	1.00	0.38	0.00	1.00	-1.67	0.81
PM	0.60	1.00	0.49	0.00	1.00	-0.41	-1.86

Table1 reports the descriptive statistics for dependent and independent variables. SG and CFOA are M&A performance measures. BI, CEOd and BS are the CG variables. FS shows the size of the firm and is proxied by natural log of total assets of a firm. IR is the M&A is industry related or not. PM is the proxy for post-M&A.

Correlation Results

It shows a negative and insignificant relationship between SG and CFOA, which suggests that rising CFOA prices without increasing sales means market power is used (Kumar, 1984 cited in Majumdar et al., 2007). Board, CEO, and BI size have no statistically significant relationship with SG or CFOA. That is, board size, CEO/Chairman duality, and BI have no impact on M&A firm performance. This supports Ghosh, Huang, and Petrova (2012). However, this result contradicts Afza and Nazir's findings (2012). CEOd is positively correlated with BS. FS also has a negative and significant correlation coefficient with SG (p-value 0.1) and CFOA (p-value 0.05). This means that the acquiring firm's SG and CFOA values are lowered. This association contradicts Afza and Nazir (2012) findings that large firms perform well. FS is positively correlated with BI. This result suggests that firm size affects BI positively. The results of IR and PM show no significant relationship with SG and CFOA, indicating that whether the merged firms are in the same industry or not has no impact on their financial performance. According to Afza et al. (2012) and Carline, Linn et al. (2009), no performance change occurs whether the acquiring firms are related or not.

Table 2 : Correlations for the Dependent and Independent Variables

Variables	Log SG	CFOA	BS	CEOd	BI	FS	IR
CFOA	-0.144 (0.133)						
BS	0.129 (0.181)	0.031 (0.748)					
CEOd							
BI	-0.094 (0.330)	-0.113 (0.241)	0.291 (0.002)				
FS							
IR	-0.038 (0.690)	-0.023 (0.809)	0.018 (0.852)	0.093 (0.333)			
PM	-0.166 (0.083)	-0.260 (0.006)	-0.038 (0.697)	0.095 (0.325)	0.223 (0.019)		
	0.051 (0.600)	-0.024 (0.804)	0.115 (0.232)	-0.094 (0.328)	0.119 (0.217)	-0.052 (0.586)	
	-0.119 (0.215)	0.036 (0.707)	-0.064 (0.504)	0.023 (0.809)	0.054 (0.575)	-0.005 (0.963)	-0.000 (1.000)

Table2 reports correlations for the dependent and independent variables. SG and CFOA are M&A financial performance measures. BI, CEOd and BS are the CG variables. FS shows the size of the firm and is proxied by natural log of total assets of a firm. IR is the M&A is industry related or not. PM is the proxy for post-M&A. The first row for each variable represents the correlation coefficients while the second row indicates their level of significance (P-value) given in italics.

Multivariate Regression Results

The regression model in this study is based on the assumption that M&A financial performance is affected by CG. For example, Afza and Nazir (2012) argue that effective CG mechanism enhances the performance of the firms especially M&A firms.

The result of the association of BS, CEOd and BI with both SG and CFOA is statistically not significant. This means that size of the board have no impact on M&A performance (SG and CFOA) of acquiring firms.

Furthermore, it can be concluded that a person holding both CEO and Chairman posts does not affect the performance of M&A firms. This association is in support of Masulis et al. (2007) and Ghosh, Huang and Petrova (2012). The association of PM with SG is negative and statistically significant ($p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$), while positive and statistically significant association ($p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$) with CFOA, which means that after M&A the SG decreases while the CFOA increases. A potential reason of this association could be an increase in price does not change the sales but may result in an increase in cash flow from operations (Kumar, 1984 cited in Majumdar et al., 2007). The interactions variables of PM with CG variables (PM*BS) shows statistically significant results for both SG and CFOA. The interaction of PM and BS shows a positive relation with SG and it shows a negative association with CFOA. These result suggest that BS has positive impact on SG and negative impact on CFOA. On the other hand, the interaction of PM and CEOd shows no significant result for both SG and CFOA, whereas, the interaction variable PM*BI shows only significance for SG. The association between PM*BI and SG is negative, this means that independence of board has negative impact on post-merger SG. Furthermore, the association of FS and IR with both SG and CFOA is not significant. This result is consistent with the study of Carline et al. (2009) and Manafi, Mahmoudian and Zabihi (2015) who conclude that FS and IR have no significant impact on change in firm performance. Moreover, the results for the years and IND are not consistent and indicates different relations with M&A performance.

Table 3: Multivariate regression results for the association of CG with financial Performance of Acquiring Firms

Variables	Log SG			CFOA	
Intercept	0.88	(0.550)	0.06	-6.02	(0.099)
BS		(0.683)	0.57	0.57	(0.135)
CEOd		(0.214)	0.70	-0.07	
BI		(0.164)	-3.26	(0.949)	1.55
		(0.003)	0.44	(0.205)	8.54
PM	-0.59	(0.116)	-1.31	(0.002)	-
		(0.018)	0.08	(0.348)	
PM*BS	0.00	(1.000)		1.06	(0.002)
				0.21	(0.813)
PM*CEOd				-1.03	(0.439)
				-0.02	(0.908)
PM*BI				0.00	(1.000)
FS					
IR					
IND	Controlled				
YEAR	Controlled				
F-Statistics	1.75 (0.029)			1.68 (0.040)	
Adj R ²	15.3%			14.0%	

Table 3 reports the regression results for model 1. SG and CFOA are M&A financial performance measures. BI, CEOd and BS are the CG variables. FS shows the size of the firm and is proxied by natural log of total assets of a firm. IR is the M&A is industry related or not. PM is the proxy for post-M&A. The PM*BS, PM*CEOd, PM*BI are the interactions of BS, CEOd and BI with PM variable, respectively. The first row for all the variables shows the regression coefficients while second row represents their respective P-values. F-statistics indicating the significance while Adj R² is the explanatory power of the regression model.

Conclusion

The purpose of this research is to provide evidence on the impact of CG on the performance of M&A firms. Prior studies did not use SG and CFOA as proxies for measuring M&A performance; instead, they used different proxies (for example, Tobin's q, ROA, ROS, ROE) to measure M&A performance. Following in the footsteps of Afza and Nazir (2012), the current study seeks to fill a research gap by investigating the impact of CG mechanisms on financial performance changes following M&A in Pakistan's non-financial sector.

From the regression results of dependent and independent variables in model 1, the relation of BS, CEOd and BI with both SG and CFOA is statistically not significant. This association suggests that the size of the board, whether both the positions (i-e CEO and Chairman) held by the same individual or by separate individuals in the firm and independence of board have no impact on firm SG and CFOA. Furthermore, the control variable FS and IR has statistically no impact on both SG and CFOA. This result concludes that size of the firm and whether the merging firm belongs to the same or different industry does not affect the performance of the acquiring firms. Moreover, the study finds that PM has significantly negative association with SG and positively

associated with CFOA, which suggests that the value of CFOA increases without an increase in SG, suggesting that the prices are being increased. The interaction variable such as PM*BS shows statistically significant result for both SG and CFOA. The interaction variable PM*BS has a positive relationship with SG but a negative relationship with CFOA. Thus, it is concluded that size of the board has positive impact on SG and on CFOA it has negative impact. However, the interaction variable PM*CEOd shows no significance for financial performance of acquiring firms. Alternatively, the interaction of PM and BI is negatively significant for SG. This association shows that the independence of board has negative impact on post-merger SG.

Overall, these results suggest that CG is a value enhancing mechanism for M&A financial performance in Pakistan. The results imply that CG reduces the agency conflicts and increases the protection of shareholders rights. Therefore, the results are consistent with previous studies, which conclude that CG enhances M&A performance (Carline et al., 2009; Afza & Nazir, 2012; Liu & Wang, 2013).

The current study also provides some useful consequences for company managers, investors and for regulators. In non-financial sector of Pakistan, the effective CG mechanism of acquiring firm's bring a positive change in performance regarding M&A.

This study highlights some potential areas for future research. The current study investigates M&A performance with respect to acquiring firms. However, the target firms needs to be investigated. This will be a good research area to find the effect of CG on M&A performance of target firms. Second, this study is limited to the use of CG variable, other CG variables could also be investigated for M&A performance such as outside dominated board, block holders, CEO compensation and audit committee etc.

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